

Mechanism of Chloramine-B Oxidation of Cycloalkanones in Hydrochloric and Perchloric Acid Media

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The kinetics of oxidation of cycloalkanones, viz. cyclopentanone (Cyp) and cyclohexanone (Cyh) by sodium *N*-chlorobenzene sulphonamide or chloramine-B (CAB) in hydrochloric and perchloric acid media have been studied at 30°. The rate shows a first order dependence each on [oxidant], [cycloalkanone] and [H⁺]. Variation of ionic strength of the medium, addition of the reaction product (benzenesulphonamide) and chloride ion have no effect on the rate. The effect of varying alcohol composition on the rate has been investigated. Plausible mechanism has been proposed in consistent with the experimental results.

KINETIC investigations involving aliphatic, cyclic, aromatic ketones and various oxidising agents¹⁻⁵ have been reported. The present paper incorporates the mechanism of oxidation of two cycloalkanones (S), viz. cyclopentanone (Cyp) and cyclohexanone (Cyh), by the less widely used but potent oxidising agent chloramine-B (CAB) in hydrochloric and perchloric acid media.

Experimental

Chloramine-B was prepared by the literature method. Its aqueous solution was standardised iodometrically and preserved in brown-coloured bottles. Cyclopentanone (E. Merck) was used as such, while cyclohexanone (B.D.H.) was used after redistillation. The solutions of the above cycloalkanones in alcohol were prepared. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Kinetic measurements: A solution containing the requisite amount of substrate, acid, sodium perchlorate (to keep the ionic strength constant), alcohol (30% in Cyp and 20% in Cyh) and water (to keep the total volume constant throughout) was equilibrated at 30°. To it was rapidly added a measured quantity of CAB solution pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating iodometrically the unconsumed CAB present in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture withdrawn at regular time intervals.

The results of stoichiometric runs indicated that one mole of cycloalkanone consumed two moles of CAB in accordance with equation (1),

where, $n=1$ in Cyp and $n=2$ in Cyh.

Benzene sulphonamide among the reaction products was detected by tlc. A mixture of petroleum ether, chloroform and *n*-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) was used as the solvent and iodine as the developing reagent ($R_f=0.88$). The corresponding 1,2-diketones were identified by spot-tests⁶ and by preparing their dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) derivatives. The products were further confirmed by their pmr spectrum.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of cycloalkanones by CAB were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants in hydrochloric and perchloric acid media.

With the cycloalkanones in large excess, plots of $\log [CAB]_t$ vs time are found to be linear indicating first order dependence on [oxidant] (Table 1). The rate was first order in [substrate] as was noticed by plotting $\log k$ vs $\log [Cyp]$ or $\log [Cyh]$. Further, a plot of k_{obs} vs [S] was linear passing

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS ON THE RATE OF REACTION AT 30°

[HCl] or [HClO₄] = 0.05 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, ethanol % = 30 in Cyp and 20 in Cyh

[CAB] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	[S] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$k (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			
		Cyclopentanone		Cyclohexanone	
		HCl	HClO ₄	HCl	HClO ₄
3.0	5.0	1.54	1.31	4.61	3.82
4.0	5.0	1.54	1.31	4.66	3.75
5.0	5.0	1.52	1.29	4.68	3.71
6.0	5.0	1.52	1.29	4.63	3.79
7.0	5.0	1.50	1.27	4.55	3.59
5.0	2.0	0.59	0.44	1.84	1.76
5.0	8.0	2.48	2.10	7.34	6.11
5.0	12.0	3.38	2.95	10.36	9.47
5.0	15.0	4.23	3.56	12.79	11.31
5.0 ^a	5.0	1.52	1.30	4.77	3.96
5.0 ^b	5.0	1.53	1.28	4.72	3.96

^aAt ionic strength 1.0 mol dm⁻³. ^bIn presence of excess benzene sulphonamide.

through the origin (Fig. 1) confirming first order dependence on cycloalkanones. The rate of reaction increased with the increase in $[H^+]$. A plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [H^+]$ was linear with unit slope indicating first order dependence in $[H^+]$. The plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ was linear passing through the origin (Fig. 2) confirming first order dependence in $[H^+]$ in both the cases. It was observed that the addition of sodium chloride to the reaction mixture had no effect on the rate of the reaction in both the cases. Addition of the reaction product (benzene sulphonamide) or variation of ionic strength of the medium (Table 1) had no effect on the rate. The solvent composition was varied by adding ethanol and the rate decreased with the increase in ethanol content of the reaction mixture. A plot of $\log k$ vs $1/D$ (where D is the dielectric constant of the medium) gave a straight line with a negative slope (Fig. 3).

The reaction was studied at different temperatures (303–316.3 K). Activation parameters were computed from the linear plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ (Table 2).

The following equilibria⁷ are reported to exist in acidified CAB solution similar to chloramine-T (CAT),

where, $R = C_6H_4SO_2$.

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} vs $[S]$, $[CAB] = 0.005 M$, $[H] = 0.05 M$, $\mu = 0.5 M$, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, EtOH % = 30 in Cyp and 20 in Cyh.

Fig. 2. Plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$, $[CAB] = 0.005 M$, $[S] = 0.05 M$, $\mu = 0.5 M$, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, EtOH % = 30 in Cyp and 20 in Cyh.

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log k$ vs $1/D$, $[CAB] = 0.005 M$, $[S] = 0.05 M$, $[H^+] = 0.05 M$, $\mu = 0.5 M$, temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$: a(i) and b(i) Cyp and Cyh in HCl, and a(ii) and b(ii) Cyp and Cyh in $HOIO_4$, in all the cases.

TABLE 2—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Parameters	Cyclopentanone		Cyclohexanone	
	HOCl	HOCl ₂	HOCl	HOCl ₂
log <i>A</i>	12.2 ± 0.01	7.4 ± 0.02	8.2 ± 0.04	10.0 ± 0.03
Δ <i>H</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	75.2 ± 0.04	47.5 ± 0.06	43.3 ± 0.02	54.1 ± 0.03
Δ <i>G</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	96.9 ± 0.4	98.1 ± 0.6	93.9 ± 0.4	94.3 ± 0.3
Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-70.1 ± 0.3	-161.6 ± 0.5	-164.8 ± 0.6	-130.9 ± 0.6

In an acidified solution of CAB, the possible oxidising species are RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl or CAB. If RNCl₂ were to be the reactive species, the rate law predicts a second order dependence of rate on [CAB] which is contrary to the experimental observations. If HOCl were to be the active species, a first order retardation of the rate by the added benzene sulphonamide would be expected, but no such effect has been noticed. Further, if RNHCl were to be the active species, a fractional order dependence with respect to [S] would have been observed, which is contrary to the experimental results. Hence, it is the CAB itself that participates in these oxidations. The oxidation of cycloalkanones by CAB is explained in Scheme 1.

In the present investigations oxidation of cycloalkanones shows a first order dependence each on [oxidant], [S] and [H⁺]. Cycloalkanones form oxonium salts on protonation in the presence of strong acids leading to enolisation,

where, *n* = 1 in Cyp and *n* = 2 in Cyh, and S represents the cycloalkanone and S' the conjugate acid.

The following mechanism is suggested for the acid-catalysed oxidation of the cycloalkanones by CAB,

Scheme 1

Application of steady state treatment to [S'] and assuming $k_{-1} \gg k_2$ [CAB], the rate law is

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAB}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{H}^+][\text{CAB}]}{k_{-1}} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) can be transformed into

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{H}^+][\text{S}]}{k_{-1}} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 [\text{H}^+][\text{S}]} \quad (14)$$

The above mechanism is supported by the following experimental observation. (i) The rate law derived above, is in accordance with the experimental results. (ii) The experimental stoichiometry is in good agreement with the proposed mechanism. (iii) The ionic strength of the medium was varied from 0.5 to 1.0 *M*. It was found that variation of ionic strength of the medium had a negligible effect on the rate of the reaction (Table 1). [Cl⁻] was varied by adding sodium chloride keeping [H⁺] constant. This variation had no effect on the rate of the reaction. Also, addition of the reaction product (benzene sulphonamide) to the reaction mixture had no significant effect on the rate of the reaction. These facts support the above mechanism. (iv) A plot of 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] at constant [S] gave a straight line passing through the origin. At constant [H⁺], a straight line graph passing through the origin was obtained by plotting 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[S]. This is in accordance with the observed experimental results and the proposed mechanism. (v) The proposed mechanism is also supported by the activation parameters. Fairly high positive values of Δ*G*[‡] and Δ*H*[‡] indicate that the transition state is highly solvated. The large negative values of Δ*S*[‡] indicate that the transition state is rigid. (vi) Amis and Jaffe⁹ have shown that

$$\log k'_D = \log k' + \frac{Z_+ \mu}{2.303 k T r^2 D} \quad (15)$$

where, *k*'_D is a function of dielectric constant *D*, *Z*₊ the charge on the ion, *μ* the dipole moment, *k* the Boltzmann constant, *T* the absolute temperature and *r* the distance of approach. Equation (15) predicts a linear relationship between log *k*'_D and 1/*D*. The slope of the line should be negative for a reaction between either a negative ion and a dipole or a dipole and a dipole, while a positive slope is obtained for a positive ion-dipole reactions. In the present investigation, the rate decreases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium which is in conformity with Amis and Jaffe and other concepts⁹.

The formation of 1,2-diketones was confirmed by taking the pmr spectra. A triplet due to the proton in position-3 is found at δ 5.2, and a singlet at δ 7.2 due to the enolic OH which is in equilibrium with the ketonic form of the 1,2-diketone were observed.

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